

BESTIALITY AS REVEALED THROUGH EROTIC SCULPTURES OF TEMPLES AND SECULAR BUILDINGS IN TAMIL NADU

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Received: May 16, 2025

Accepted: Jun 10, 2025

Published: Jun 16, 2025

ABSTRACT

What is attempted in this paper is a study on bestiality and eroticism as found in Hindu temple walls and public baths in Tamil Nadu. The term “bestiality” can be defined as the intercourse occurring between a human being and an animal. In general, a donkey, pig, goat, dog, or a cat is chosen for this purpose because of its docile nature and the convenient size of its sexual organ. *Zoophilia* is defined as an unnatural, abnormal sexual attraction of humans towards animals. Bestiality or *Zoophilia* has been in practice in many countries since the inception of civilization. This kind of sexual relationship can be found in many cultures through the ages. Some of the surviving artwork in Indian temples depicts a few scenes of bestial relationship providing evidences for the prevalence of such amorous bestial practices among the men and women of those days. They provide a clear visual representation of the cultural and religious practices of people of ancient and mediaeval India. The portrayal of bestiality in art and religious literature mirrors the cultural life of people. The sculptures in the Sun Temple at Konark, Odisha, Kedareswara temple at Bellagavi, Karnataka and temples at Khajuraho, Madhya Pradesh exhibit open and amorous forms of sexual indulgence between human beings and domestic animals. Chinnaiyampettai Public bath at Thiruvannamalai Dist., Tamil Nadu, exhibits a series of erotic sculptures in a panel near the steps of the parapet walls. The scenes of bestiality must have been carved during the Nayak period, probably in the 17th century C.E. In addition, the researcher identifies probable reasons for displaying scenes of amorous sexual acts and bestiality in the form of sculptures in places where the general public gathered for performing various duties on different occasions.

Key words: Bestiality, Zoophilia, Khajuraho, Chinnaiyanpet, Nymphomania, Tantrism

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I. INTRODUCTION

Human society grew up with the support of domestic animals which provided food, clothes, assistance in hunting, entertainment and labor for their domestic and occupational purposes. Zoophilie has been a common concept across various cultures and religions, indicating that bestiality was historically recognized and accepted by many ancient civilizations. Webster's New World College Dictionary defines bestiality as sexual relations between a person and an animal. Many paintings, drawings on the rocks, sculptures, literature and folklore reveal that men and women were in intimate sexual relationship with animals. Mythologies provide tales of human-animal unions and instances of many gods and goddesses born out of such strange sexual relationships. This paper examines ancient and medieval society's attitude towards bestiality as revealed in sculptures and oral literature, in order to understand the social life of the people who practiced bestiality. Very few studies have been made on this much tabooed topic even by social anthropologists. However, the practice of bestiality has been prevalent in the modern society and so abnormal psychologists and medical doctors who treat abnormal sexual behavior of their patients, are currently interested in bestiality, and do many case studies in this area. From the point of view of social anthropology and history of Indian culture, this kind of study will pave the way for further research on the unnatural sexual behavior of ancient people, isolated tribes and even modern communities, and finding reasons for making bestiality a punishable social crime.

II. BESTIALITY WIDESPREAD THROUGH THE AGES

The practice of human-animal sexual relations dates back to at least the fourth glacial age, probably between 40,000 and 25,000 years ago. Throughout the social history of mankind, bestiality has been a common practice among men and women who engaged in consensual sex with willing animals.¹ However; it is difficult to know whether the sexual relations between humans and animals were carried on with mutual consent. Prehistoric practice of bestiality is evidenced by rock art of the Stone Age.²

Furthermore, ancient civilizations which prospered in Egypt, Greece, Rome, Africa, the Middle East and Asia provide historical evidences of this practice.³ In Babylonia, King Hammurabi (1792-1750 BCE) declared death sentence to those who were engaged in bestial relationship.⁴ The book of Leviticus indicates that bestiality was widespread in the land of Canaan.⁵ Later on, the Hebrews viewed sexual relations with animals as an indication of worship of other gods, and condemned both the person and the animal involved to death.

The Egyptians and the Greeks in the ancient times practiced bestiality, as evident from the depictions on the tombs, hieroglyphics and mythology, and incorporated it into their religious practices. During religious festivals and other celebrations, Egyptian and Roman kings and queens enjoyed sexual excitement through bestial relations with cattle and other domestic animals. However, later on, bestiality became a punishable offence in Egypt. On the other hand, this practice was widespread among shepherds in Rome.⁶

There are certain reasons for the widespread practice of bestiality in various cultures. Sexual relationship with an animal occurs due to opportunity and sexual urge. For a human being, the animal is a legitimate substitute

for a sexual partner.⁷ An African tribe advised the young male adults to have sexual intercourse with a donkey or a cow as a premarital rite to show their physical fitness for their ensuing married life. Arabs believed that bestial relationship helped some young men increase the size of their sexual organs. Many Arabs encouraged men to have bestial relationship as they believed that bestiality could cure some diseases. It was also believed that bestiality could cure nymphomania.⁸ However, a detailed comparison with Avestan records provides further insights into this practices.⁹ In America and the Middle East bestiality was encouraged among men as it was thought to prevent adultery. The acceptance of bestiality varied among tribes but the practice was socially accepted and not punished among the tribes of Navajo, Crow, Hopi, Plains Indians, the Canadian Saulteaux tribe, the Kufer and the Copper Eskimos.¹⁰

III. BESTIALITY IN INDIA

As in the case of other countries in the world, bestiality was practiced in India. However, it remained a provocative and controversial issue. Many sexologists expressed that it was highly prevalent in rural and agrarian communities which lived in close proximity with such domesticated animals as dogs, goats, sheep, donkeys and cats. A seal found in the site of Indus Valley civilization shows a half-sitting figure indulging in sexual intercourse with a phallic-headed crocodile and this provides an evidence for the practice of bestiality in India even before 5000 years.¹¹ In ancient India, belief in the transmigration of souls between animals and humans was a sign of acceptance of bestiality. Indian mythology, as in the cases of Greek and other European cultures, often integrates human and animal forms, for example *yali*, similar to sphinx, suggesting a mixed-parentage. According to a legendary story Prajapathi co-habituated with Usha, the goddess of Dawn, but the goddess tried to escape from the world by transforming herself into various animal forms. Yet Prajapathi could identify her and had sexual pleasure with her. As a result, this copulation was believed to have produced some other animal species.¹² Pet dogs and monkeys were kept as pets in harems for providing company and sexual gratification for women. We find references to Prasenajit in Hindu Philosophy, who used a nanny-goat for sexual gratification while his wife sought pleasure with a pet dog.¹³ Vedas and legends abound with instances of bestiality.¹⁴ However, the Bhagavata Purana and Devi Bhagavata Purana, the religious legends of India, condemn bestiality and for instance, they assert that humans engaging in sexual relations with animals, especially cows, will lead themselves to eternal damnation.¹⁵ This literary reference indicates significant prevalence of bestiality in ancient India.¹⁶ To support this view, the Code of Manu (*Manu Needhi*) stipulates that an individual who commits a bestial act must undergo a penance known as *Samtapana Krikkhra*.¹⁷ Kaudilya in his treatise, *Arthasastra*, punishes a wretch who carnally approaches animals with *12 panas* (a monetary value) which is much less than the penalty levied for a human who has anal intercourse with another human.¹⁸ Hindu tradition, as in the case of medieval Greek legends, depicts bestiality in paintings and sculptures. In this instance, the sexual act between a human and an animal was interpreted as divine union and it was believed that the human being was elevating himself to a level of divinity while having such a relationship with a deity which had incarnated in the form of an animal. Moreover, a human when copulating a sacred cow or monkey, believed that it would bring favourable outcome or good fortune.¹⁹ Additionally, there are references to ritualistic practices where women engaged in masturbation and performed fellatio with bulls. Moreover, there are instances which say that open sexual activities were performed during certain religious festivals.²⁰ There is a reference about

Tamil community in Sri Lanka, which mentions that it has been a common practice for humans having sex with goats and cows.²¹ This kind of practices were common in nomadic tribes in Sri Lanka in those days, and may be prevalent among cattle-farming communities even today.²

IV. AMOROUS SCULPTURES ALONG WITH OCCASIONAL BESTIAL DEPICTIONS

India has been renowned for its temples which document both secular and spiritual aspects of human life. Many ancient Hindu temples often incorporate erotic sculptures, nude male and female sculptures, and partly embellished nude divine forms. In fact, nudity is a common motif in the paintings and sculptures of the temple premises. Pretty damsels from heaven are presented with remarkable accuracy of physical features in rock-cut monastic caves of Ajanta in Maharashtra, which date back from 2nd century BCE to 8th century BCE²³ and Ellora from the 5th century BCE to 10th century BCE.²⁴ Along with these sculpted art forms, scenes of bestiality also are exhibited on the panels of temple walls. Tripurantaka Temple at Balligavi, Shimoga in Karnataka has a striking carving, which depicts a man engaging in sexual intercourse with a pig.²⁵

Khajuraho, a small town in Madhya Pradesh, stands out as a prominent location where some of the most explicit examples of amorous art are found in temples. In recognition of their artistic, architectural and sculptural significance, UNESCO declared the elegantly carved Hindu temples of Khajuraho a World Heritage Site in 1986. Visitors to these temples are greeted with a profusion of intricate sculptures adorning every inch of the outer walls. Among these sculptures we could witness various gods, goddesses, warriors, musicians, animals, birds and floral designs. Numerous carvings found in these temples are of an intensely erotic nature depicting love-making scenes involving men, women and animals. In the Lakshmana temple in Khajuraho, various erotic scenes depicted on the walls include scenes of bestiality. Interestingly, these depictions of bestiality are juxtaposed with sculptures of divine beings. The Chandala kings, who patronized the construction of these temples were followers of Tantric principles which include practice of yoga to attain the state of supreme bliss through some esoteric or erotic techniques. They actively promoted their faith through the temples they commissioned.²⁶

The Gommateshwara statue is a 57-foot (17 m) high monolithic male sculpture on Vindhya giri hill in the town of Shravanbelagola, Karnataka. Exquisitely carved out of a single block of granite, it is one of the tallest monolithic statues in the ancient world. The nude male figure illustrates the state of liberation of a Jain monk who had renounced all his possessions including clothes. A Jain inscription here warns vandals, cautioning them about the punishment that awaits those who deface historical inscriptions. The punishment mentioned here says the man would be asked to mate with a donkey.²⁷ Even before sexual expressions in common places was considered a taboo, voluptuous sculptures in intimate scenes were etched in temples across the country.

Why did the patrons of art encourage the extra-ordinarily skilled sculptors to carve the amorous sculptures on the exterior walls of holy buildings?

Temples in India were not merely places of worship, but also centers of learning. They teach the nuances of carving on the medium of stone with a sound knowledge about the physiognomy of men, women, animals and birds. Moreover, Hindu philosophy advocates four goals for a human being to be achieved Dharma (learning and leading a

life of righteousness), Artha (earning sufficient wealth through right means), Kama (enjoying physical pleasures through different kinds of sexual fantasies) and Moksha (eternal state of liberation).

Vatsyayana was an ancient philosopher who lived in the fifth century CE and authored “Kama Sutra”. It is a treatise on conjugal love, illustrating the erotic fantasies of men and women. We must remember that polygamy and polyandry were practiced for various reasons in the Indian subcontinent on those days.²⁸ Apart from other artistic presentations, Lingaraja temple in Bhubaneswar, Odisha displays various ecstatic images illustrating the theory expounded in “Kama Sutra”.²⁹ Virupaksha temple in Karnataka presents an exquisite example of construction, and boasts of erotic forms on the outer walls.³⁰ The chief aim of these sculptures is to make people admire nudity and polygamous relationships. There is a theory in psychology which states that if a human being is not mature enough to understand the sanctity of love-lust relationship (conjugal love) a human being cannot lead a successful family life.

Some social psychologists, who have observed the well-developed physical features of amorous sculptures in the temples, explain that child marriage was widely practiced in rural communities and agrarian families in order to strengthen the unity in their respective communities. Such immature couples (children) were given sex education through these erotic sculptures on the walls of temples. This was important in order to create awareness about significance of conjugal love for the procreation of progeny.

Another theory states that erotic sculptures were placed on the outer walls of temples in order to insist that visitors must leave their sexual desires outside the temple before entering the holy place for worship. That is why the inner walls are plain without any embellishment of erotic art. Psychologically, these sensuous images satisfy the filthy desires of visitors whose minds should be free from sensual worldly pleasures, before offering their prayers to god or goddess.³¹

V. BESTIALITY IN PUBLIC BATHS IN TAMIL NADU

In general, bestial scenes are rarely found in Tamil Nadu. However, a public bath (Fig.1) at Chinnaiyanpettai, Thiruvannamalai district has panels of amorous and bestial scenes on the walls of the Public Bath of 17th century CE.

(Fig.1)

A local chieftain Chinnaiyan built it during the Nayak period.³² The carvings in the tank have men and women who are engaged in sexual intercourse and some of them depict bestial scenes (Fig.2). The Chinnaiyanpettai tank has more than a hundred erotic images carved on stone walls.

(Fig.2)

These bestial panels illustrate the role of animals as sources of emotional support and companionship and unconventional practices of sexual relationship between human beings and domestic animals. On the panel of a wall of the tank, there is a carving which presents a donkey inserting its genitals into the vagina of a woman who is washing the clothes (Fig.3).

(Fig.3)

In another carving a male dog is climbing on the back of a woman who is cooking and it is noteworthy that the woman is not showing any aversion towards the act of the animal (Fig.4).

(Fig.4)

Another carving presents a nude girl exposing her breasts and vagina as if inviting a man for sexual act (Fig.5). There are some carvings where men are enjoying the animals which look like jenny (female donkey) (Fig.6) and doe (female goat).

(Fig.5)

Moreover, yet another carving presents a dancing girl who is holding a snake-like creature in her hand while a man is trying to molest her sexually. In another scene, a man and two women as a group are trying to insert a long thin stick into the vagina of another girl who is in a reclining position on the ground. In short, these sculptures depict sexual intercourse between a man and a woman; a man with a few women; one woman with a few men and a few motifs of bestiality. The researchers point out that there are many tanks built about 300 to 400 years before, which display the sexual acts of different partners explicitly. It is noted that the Nayak period is known as Erotic Age in Indian art history because of erotic sculptures are found in the temples of Nayaks.

What could be the reasons for showing sexual demos on the secular buildings like the tank in Chinnayanpettai?

Secular art is one that does not have a religious theme. However, almost all Indian art had some sort of religious or social theme to it. Thus, secular art can be defined as art that has no religious reference and is, in fact, there is no connotation to any organized religion. With an aesthetic appeal in a non-religious context, it points out some social aspects and problems.

Sociologists admit that marriage is a regulating institution for a healthy family life, providing a disciplined social structure. While there are men with excessive desire for sex, there are also nymphos among women. On the contrary, there are men and women who do not have any sexual desire, even though they accept marriage as a necessary institution in a community. These public baths or specially constructed tanks for public utility address the problems of the latter group of members in the society.

In order to support the view, a local folk-lore explains the probable reason for such a public tank at Chinnaiyampettai. A battle was about to break out between Chinnaiyan, the local king and the chieftain of neighbouring Padaveedu. In order to avoid this conflict, Chinnaiyan decided to give his young daughter in marriage to the son of the Padaveedu Chieftain. The bride was too young to get married. After the wedding, the husband wanted to consummate the marriage. The bride was much scared and unwilling to have any sex with her husband. So she returned to her father's palace. The father was worried and tried to teach his daughter the significance of conjugal love and provide sex-education through her elderly friends. But the child-bride did not understand it. The king consulted his minister who advised him to make arrangements for constructing a big tank with stone walls where various amorous sculptures could be carved. The daughter, when she went to take bath, would learn about the need for sex for a married woman. This is what we learn from the folk-tale. To prove this, a panel sculpture of this tank shows the princess travelling in palanquin.

In addition, there is another tank for public utility, with erotic sculptures engraved on the walls in Vadaseri village in Tiruppattur near Vaniyambadi. Though this one is similar to the tank in Chinnaiyanpettai, here we find a well in the middle. On the steps and along the compound walls there are floral carvings modelled after local flowers, and tiny sculptures of animals, birds and deities, worshiped by the public. It is interesting to note that scenes from the Ramayana and the Mahabharata are engraved splendidly. Along with these are erotic sculptures, signifying sexual life.

Moreover, Keezhraivanthavadi near Thandarampattu, Tiruvannamalai district has a tank similar to the one in Chinnaiyanpettai, on a 45-cent area. We find sculptures of erotic nature in this tank too. But these sculptures are in dilapidated condition, and so the Department of Archaeology, Govt. of Tamil Nadu has taken control of it and maintains the tank.

The researchers and archaeologists concluded that these tanks were likely to have been constructed about 400 years before, during the Nayak period under Vijayanagar era in Tamil Nadu. Prof. K.Mohan Gandhi points out that sculptures on the tank steps at Chinnaiyanpettai are forthright and clear, but the social reasons behind these secular buildings are not evidently clear. This could be another area for further research for scholars.

While analysing the presence of erotic and bestial sculptures in the public baths ((tanks), the current paper-presenting researcher understands and appreciates the sculpting skills of the artists who must have undergone excruciating pains when they tried to sculpt small figurines and especially while involving in the creation of amorous artwork on the lower parts of the panels.

VI. SOCIO-CULTURAL FACTORS FOR THE DEPICTION OF BESTIALITY

- Imagery bewilders the spiritual implications of sexuality. Artists portray eternity by depicting humans engaging in sexual relations with birds and pets.
- Given that zoophile behaviour was once tolerated by ancient civilizations, it could be a product of cultural relativism.
- Bestiality might have been a part of rural culture. It is an orientation of lifestyle in which both the human and animal it can be reciprocally pleasurable.
- Despite the literary allusions to bestiality, by the tenth century, artistic representations of sexuality and bestiality had undergone a fundamental transformation.
- Temples grew bigger and more elaborate, providing areas for artistic expression and all kinds of sexual imagery.
- Regionalism and the development of regional conventions strongly influenced art forms just as they influenced other aspects of cultural life.
- The presence of erotic representation may have been owing to the influence of Tantrism.
- Temples are considered the places for learning as well as worship, specially of the fine arts, including the art of love making.
- The depiction of sexual activities in temples was considered a good omen because it represented new beginnings and new life.
- Hinduism has traditionally considered sex an essential part of life.
- The shapely maidens and virile men contorting their bodies in impossible sexual positions right next to sculptures of divine beings smiling blissfully at the devout. It is believed that Indian mythology is full of instances where humans and animal forms have been integrated as if to indicate the parentage.
- The erotic art is unobjectionable when crouched with in a religious context.
- Khajuraho holds within its walls a larger lesson on tolerance for India.
- The Regional rulers like Chandela kings dictate the balance between male and female forces they promoted their faith in the temples they created.
- If bestiality is considered immoral in Indian culture, this form of art is depicted to educate about the sin of sex with other animals.

Thus, engaging in sexual acts with animals is occasionally portrayed by artists to symbolize moral corruption. Historically, bestiality was deemed a violation of natural laws and carried a death sentence. Across numerous cultures, humans are regarded as distinct from other animals, and sexual relations with animals are considered a form

of desecration. Currently, under Section 377 of the Indian Penal Code, any sexual activity that deviates from the natural order, including with animals, is punishable by life imprisonment or a prison term of up to ten years.³³

VII. CONCLUSION

To sum up, theories about the reasons for presenting erotic sculptures and scenes of bestiality in public places vary, which may be psychological, social or cultural. Medical science has been researching on the reasons for the practice of bestiality and perverted sexual behaviour in patients. Artistic presentations of bestiality throughout the world prove that mankind has always shown interest in fanciful idea of having sexual relations mainly with domestic animals. Psycho-analysts believe that fancied scenes and images arise in people's art, literature, religion and dreams as they are true reflections and representations of the archaic contents, deeply buried in their subconscious mind.

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